

1 **New UHPLC coupled to mass spectrometry approaches for screening of non-**
2 **volatile compounds as potential migrants from adhesives used in food packaging**
3 **materials**

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8

9 **Abstract**

10 The objective of this study was to identify the non-volatile compounds as potential
11 migrants from adhesives used in food packaging. A number of the current acrylic
12 adhesive formulations were extracted and prepared for analysis. The extracts were
13 screened using ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography coupled to a time of
14 flight mass spectrometer detector (UHPLC-TOF-MS). This approach allowed the
15 identification of several components by a combination of exact mass and in-source
16 collision induced dissociation (CID). Due to the lack of freely available information on
17 adhesive formulations further analyses were undertaken using ultra-high-performance
18 liquid chromatography coupled to high definition mass spectrometry (UHPLC-HDMS).
19 Using the MassFragmentTM tool to interrogate fragmentation data, a wide series of
20 compounds were identified, demonstrating the usefulness and importance of these tools
21 for difficult problems. Moreover, using several packaging materials containing
22 adhesives, qualitative migration tests were performed with Tenax[®] as a food simulant.
23 Several non-volatile compounds were identified as well in the Tenax[®] which
24 emphasizes the importance of this work and demonstrates that even the non-volatile
25 compounds have the potential to migrate into food which is in contact with packaging
26 materials. The main characteristics of the screening study and the results obtained are
27 shown and discussed.

28 **Keywords:** Food contact material, adhesive composition, Screening analysis, UHPLC-
29 TOF-MS, UHPLC-HDMS, migration, Tenax, non volatile migrants.

30

31 **1. Introduction**

32 Adhesives are used worldwide to manufacture food packages and food contact materials
33 since packaging rarely comprise a single component. They are used in packages to form
34 multilayer laminates by combination of several substrates (paper, cardboard, polymers,
35 metal foil, metalized films...), to form the geometric shape of the package and the
36 multilayer structures as well as to form labels to stick on the packages[1].

37 Like all components of food contact materials, adhesives have to compliant Article 3 of
38 EU Regulation 1935/2004 which means no transfer of substances on/into the food in
39 amounts which could endanger human health. In contrast to plastics that are regulated
40 by positive lists of authorized ingredients, adhesives have not yet a specific regulation
41 [2]. Although adhesives are often applied between two surfaces, they are not considered
42 as a layer of material, even though most of adhesive formulations contain resins and
43 polymers in their formulation. However, they take part of the whole packaging material
44 and can seriously affect the final migration performance. Taking into account this
45 approach, hundreds of raw materials would be out of scope and human health could be
46 under threat.

47 Modern-day adhesives are often fairly complex formulations of components that
48 perform specialized functions. Very few polymers are used without the addition of some
49 modifying substance. The various components that can constitute an adhesive
50 formulation include: base resin or binder, catalyst or hardeners, accelerators, inhibitors,
51 retarders, solvents, thickeners, diluents, extenders, fillers, carriers, plasticizers,
52 flexibilizers, tackifiers, film formers, antioxidants, antihydrolysis, antifungals, soaps,
53 surfactants and wetting agents [3]. This list of components gives an idea of the
54 complexity of the adhesives formulation. However, the real formulations are not known
55 and that is why powerful analytical techniques are required for screening, to identify as
56 much as possible the compounds likely related to the adhesives in a packaging material
57 and finally in migration analysis.

58 Nowadays, the identification of non-volatile compounds in complex mixtures is a
59 significant analytical challenge. Screening procedures are not very common in
60 analytical developments, probably because of the intrinsic difficulties related to them.
61 To obtain an unbiased dataset, full-spectrum acquisition techniques are required. Single-
62 and triple-quadrupole instrumentation does not provide adequate sensitivity in full-scan
63 mode when applied to samples of this nature. All quadrupole and linear ion-trap
64 instruments normally have higher sensitivity in selected ion, precursor or neutral loss
65 scan modes. However, their selectivity is low because they can only acquire nominal
66 mass spectra, a drawback that also applies to single-quadrupole and triple-quadrupole
67 mass analyzers.

68 In contrast, the time-of-flight (TOF) mass analyzer provides the selectivity and
69 sensitivity required for efficient and wide-range screening, as it combines high, full-
70 spectral sensitivity with high mass resolution so as to accurately measure the mass of
71 any ionizable components in the sample. Elemental compositions can be confidently
72 proposed with low mass errors. TOF-MS can provide a notable amount of chemical
73 information in a single experiment, so this technique is very attractive for performing
74 non-targeted analyses. It has been used broadly in many areas, such as environmental
75 and food safety analysis [4-19] but it has not been applied to adhesives yet.

76 Since adhesives are unknown complex mixtures, the most advanced techniques are
77 necessary for screening purposes to elucidate the composition.
78 Synapt HDMS developed by Waters is a technique capable to provide much structural
79 information. This equipment provides an expanded range of fragmentation protocols for
80 structural characterization studies because it provides first- and second-generation
81 product ions from a precursor in one experiment. The first generation of fragments are
82 separated by ion mobility that is a gas-phase electrophoretic technique that gives rapid
83 separations of gas-phase ions on the milliseconds timescale. The theory and applications
84 of ion mobility have been presented in many reviews [20-22]. The ions are accelerated
85 through a drift tube, under the influence of a weak electric field gradient and in the
86 presence of a neutral buffer gas (typically nitrogen, helium, or air), resulting in the
87 separation of ions on the basis of different mobilities. This technique has been mainly
88 developed to elucidate protein structure [23-26] and could be very useful in many other
89 applications such as the identification of non-target compounds in complex samples,
90 which is one of the objectives of this paper.

91 This work deals with the study carried out by Ultra-high-performance liquid
92 chromatography-time of flight-mass spectrometry (UHPLC-ESI-TOF-MS) and
93 UHPLC-ESI-high definition mass spectrometry (HDMS) to identify the non-volatile
94 compounds extracted from four different acrylic adhesives. Once the likely migrants
95 were identified, migration tests were performed and the migrants identified again in the
96 solid food simulant used for the test. The comparison of both MS approaches for the
97 identification of compounds as well as the results obtained are shown and discussed.

98

99 **2. Experimental**

100 **2.1. Materials and reagents**

101 Acetonitrile, water and methanol were from J.T. Baker (Deventer, The Netherlands).
102 Three different water based acrylic adhesives (adhesive 1, 2 and 3) were taken for the
103 analysis. The origin and main characteristics are confidential and cannot be explained
104 here. These adhesives are commonly used to make laminates consisting of two or more
105 substrates such as plastics, paper, cardboard or aluminium, glued with the adhesive
106 Several laminates commonly used in food packaging were made in the laboratory
107 according to the directions of the adhesive companies. The laminates were
108 manufactured as follows: a) a label prepared with adhesive 1 applied on aluminum and
109 polyethylene; b) a laminate made with polypropylene and polyethylene using adhesive 2
110 and c) a laminate made with polypropylene and paper using adhesive 3.
111 The standard 4-nonyl phenol ethoxilated (4-NPEO) (technical) 99.0% was from Dr
112 Ehrenstorfer GmbH (Germany).

113 **2.2. UHPLC separation**

114 Chromatography was carried out in an Acquity system using an Acquity UPLC BEH
115 C18 column of 1.7 μm particle size (2.1 x 100 mm), both from Waters (Milford, MA,
116 USA).

117 UPLC conditions were optimized in order to achieve a good chromatographic resolution
118 and sensitivity. Several parameters were tested such as the mobile phase composition.
119 Different mobile phases and different pHs ranging between acidic to basic conditions
120 were tested. Finally, acetonitrile and water were used as mobile phases.
121 Chromatography was carried out at 0.4 mL/min column flow and the column
122 temperature was 30°C. The gradient used here was 5-95% acetonitrile (0-8.5 min) and
123 the volume of sample injected was 2 μl .

124

125 **2.3. Mass spectrometry detection**

126 Firstly, it was used a time of flight mass spectrometer (TOF) LCT Premier XE from
127 Waters (Milford, MA, USA) with an electrospray probe in positive mode (ESI+) and in
128 positive mode (ESI-) in W mode. Cone voltages were optimized between 20 and 50 V,
129 finally 30 V was selected for the screening because more peaks were detected. The tune
130 MS parameters, desolvation gas temperature was 450°C and desolvation gas flow was
131 900 L h⁻¹. The MS range acquired was 100-1000 Da.

132 Secondly, a high definition mass spectrometer (HDMS) Waters SYNAPT HDMS™
133 (Waters, Milford MA, USA) was used with an electrospray probe in positive mode
134 (ESI+) and in positive mode (ESI-) in W mode. Tune parameters were the same used
135 for TOF spectrometer. Masses fragmented with this equipment were selected from the
136 spectra of the peaks obtained by UHPLC-TOF-MS. Collision energies used to fragment
137 the masses are shown in table 1.

138 MassLynx v 4.1 software (Waters, Milford MA, USA) was used to analyse the samples
139 and ChromaLynx (Waters, Milford MA, USA) was used to deconvolve the spectra.

140 **2.4. Dilution of the adhesive samples**

141 1 gram of pure adhesive sample (non cured) was extracted with 10 grams of acetonitrile.
142 When acetonitrile was added the acrylic polymer precipitated. The solution containing
143 the additives from the adhesive was filtered using a 0.22 µm pore filter. Then, samples
144 were diluted 1/100 with acetonitrile. A blank of acetonitrile and these solutions were
145 analyzed by UHPLC-TOF-MS and UHPLC-HDMS in order to identify the compounds
146 present in the adhesive.

147 **2.5. Qualitative migration tests**

148 1.7 cm² of each laminate were placed in a 7 ml vial and covered with a monolayer of
149 Tenax (approximately 20 mg). The migration from both sides of each laminate was
150 measured with Tenax in independent tests. For adhesive 1 Tenax was applied only on
151 the PE side because aluminum was considered inert and high barrier to migration. In the
152 case of adhesives 2 and 3, both sides of the laminate were studied, so that two assays
153 were done for each laminate (PP and PE for adhesive 2 and PP and paper for adhesive
154 3). Therefore, a total of 5 different migration experiments were done. Vials were closed

155 and placed in the oven at 70°C for 2 hours. Then the laminates were removed from the
156 vial and Tenax was extracted with 1.5 ml of methanol in an ultrasonic bath for 10
157 minutes. The extract was concentrated under nitrogen stream to 0.5 ml gravimetrically
158 controlled and finally this extract was analyzed by UHPLC-TOF-MS with the same
159 method used for the screening and identification of the compounds.

160 Once the identification was finished, a standard of 10 µg/g of NPEO in acetonitrile was
161 prepared and analyzed.

162 **3. Results and discussion**

163 **3.1. UHPLC-ESI-TOF-MS**

164 An AQUITY UPLC BEH C18 column was selected for this work as it was considered
165 as a universal column of choice for most UHPLC separations and very appropriate for
166 screening purposes. Chromatographic separation was optimized until resolution of
167 peaks didn't improve significantly. Acidic and basic mobile phases were used in order
168 to identify more compounds but new peaks were not found, so the work was continued
169 with the optimized conditions explained in section 2.2.

170 Figure 1 shows that there was not a common profile of compounds for the pure
171 adhesives, even though all the adhesives theoretically belong to the acrylic class. The
172 chromatograms corresponding to the extracts of adhesive 1 and adhesive 2 showed a
173 series of peaks (1-19 for adhesive 1 and 1-11 for adhesive 2) that could be polymers.
174 Moreover, some wide peaks are observed in the figure. These peaks could correspond to
175 more than one compound but it was almost impossible to separate them using this
176 column. UHPLC offers much narrower peaks and better separation of compounds in
177 complex mixtures than standard HPLC. However even after optimizing both the mobile
178 phase and the chromatographic conditions, the samples under study were so complex
179 that resolution of individual compounds was complicated. The use of high resolution
180 MS maintained the possibility to identify individual compounds on the spectra in the
181 absence of perfect chromatographic separation. In this case, TOF-MS was essential for
182 gaining the necessary information about the compounds of interest. ESI probe was
183 selected because the compounds were supposed to be polar compounds as they were in
184 the water base acrylic adhesives that was considered a polar medium. Both positive and

185 negative modes were used but no compounds were identified with ESI negative mode.
186 The MS range acquired was 100-1000 Da because it was considered that it is unlikely
187 that masses bigger than 1000 Da would migrate from the adhesive to the food.

188 Each adhesive was compared to the blank with the help of ChromaLynx software. This
189 software deconvolved the spectra and provided a list with the retention times, accurate
190 mass and abundance of each mass detected by the equipment. Then the comparison of
191 the data to the blank in each case provided the list of masses that were only present in
192 the adhesives. Once the list of accurate masses of each adhesive were known, different
193 possibilities for elemental composition were established considering that the molecules
194 were formed with the most common element (C,H,O,N,Cl,S,Br,Na). Na, which was
195 present in the mobile phase, was also considered as often the molecules form adducts
196 with it.

197 Once different options for elemental composition of each accurate mass were known it
198 was necessary to know the typical composition of an acrylic adhesive in order to
199 elucidate the possible compounds that could be present. Acrylic adhesive formulation
200 may include the following additives: monomer, catalyzers, plasticizers, surfactants,
201 fillers, stickers, adhesion promotors and tougheners among others. The most common
202 monomer is methyl methacrylate and the most common catalyst is a tertiary amine.
203 Plasticizers include the less volatile phthalates, adipates, sebacates, phosphates, and
204 other ester types. There are many types of surfactants that can be ionic and non-ionic.
205 Common fillers are wood flour, silica, alumina, titanium oxide, metal powders, glass
206 fibers...Tougheners can be chlorosulphonated polyethylene, acrylonitrile elastomeric
207 copolymers and polyurethane elastomers. This description of additives used in the
208 formulation of adhesives is very general and brief but it is worth to point out that there
209 are thousands of additives that can be used in adhesive systems and new formulations
210 bring out constantly in the market. The choice depends on the composition of the
211 adhesive, on how it will be used, the substrates on which they will be applied to, the
212 cost, and the properties that need to be obtained[3].

213 Since the composition was unknown, the identification of single compounds was a
214 difficult task. Nevertheless, for the masses that were supposed to be polymers, the mass
215 difference between each polymer masses was calculated and the comparison of

216 elemental composition for each polymer was done. This way the identification of some
217 polymers present in the adhesive was achieved (table 2). For instance, in adhesive 1
218 from mass 173.0790 Da (peak 1) to mass 965.5523 Da (peak 19) it was found that the
219 elemental composition ranged from $C_6H_{14}O_4Na$ to $C_{42}H_{86}O_{22}Na$, with a difference
220 between the measured accurate mass of each polymer of the series of 44.0262 Da
221 corresponding to one unit of C_2H_4O . Then, a bibliographic search was done among the
222 possible additives in the adhesive that could be of polymeric nature with this elemental
223 composition and with this mass difference between each polymer of the series. This
224 series of polymers corresponds to Polyethylene glycol (PEG). PEG with a molecular
225 weight of about 200-800 Da is usually employed as plasticizer in pressure sensitive
226 adhesives, like the acrylic adhesives that were studied in this work [27].

227 This procedure was applied to all the polymers detected in the adhesive and most of
228 them were identified. In adhesive 2, the elemental composition of peaks from 1 to 11
229 ranged from $C_{12}H_{24}O_4Na$ to $C_{42}H_{84}O_{14}$ with a measured mass difference of 58.0419
230 corresponding to one unit of C_3H_6O between each polymer of the series. This accurate
231 mass difference corresponds to propylene oxide that is the repeating unit in poly
232 (propylene oxide). This polymer is used in the production of polyurethanes[28] that
233 could be used as tougheners in acrylic adhesives, as a plasticizer in pressure-sensitive
234 adhesives [27] and also as a non-ionic polymerisable surfactant in combination with
235 ethylene oxide[29].

236 Octyl phenol ethoxylate (OPEO) and nonylphenol ethoxylate (NPEO) that are non-ionic
237 surfactants [30] were among them but in this case, each polymer could not be separated
238 by liquid chromatography using this method. They were identified through their spectra
239 (Figure 2). This figure shows NPEO spectrum, where the typical shape of a polymer
240 spectrum is observed. The study of the difference in the accurate masses and the
241 knowledge of adhesives that could contain surfactants like these, drove to the
242 identification of NPEO. This compound, used as nonionic surfactant, is suspected to
243 have endocrine disrupting properties and cause harmful effects, including feminization
244 and carcinogenesis on various organisms [31]. As a result, the migration study of this
245 compound from the packaging that contain the adhesive to the food is necessary
246 according to the European Commission [32].

247 3.2. UHPLC-ESI-HDMS

248 As has been above explained, the identification of single compounds was a difficult task
249 using UHPLC-ESI-TOF-MS, since adhesive composition is unknown and it is difficult
250 to assure the identity of a compound with only the information of accurate mass. For
251 this reason, UHPLC-ESI-HDMS was used. This analytical technique facilitates
252 acquisition of accurate mass, selected ion fragmentation and matrix interference
253 reduction using ion mobility. It provides the first and second generation product ions
254 from a precursor in one experiment, so maximizes the information content from each
255 sample. It uses a quadrupole to select the masses and then three T-Wave™ ion guides
256 trap ions, separate them by their ion mobility, and transfer them to the orthogonal
257 acceleration time-of-flight analyzer for high-resolution mass analysis. The trap and
258 transfer regions can also be used for fragmentation analyses. Firstly, the selected
259 precursor ions are fragmented in the trap region, these fragments are separated by ion
260 mobility spectrometry and then, a second generation of fragments are produced in the
261 transfer region. Finally, first and second generation of ions are time aligned. Data
262 interpretation is facilitated with the help of DriftScope™ Mobility Environment
263 Software (v2.0) (Waters, Milford MA, USA).

264 In this work, UHPLC and MS conditions optimized for UHPLC-TOF-MS were applied.
265 Then, optimization of the first fragmentation was done. The trap region allowed
266 working with collision energy ramps, optimum values are shown in table 1. Once first
267 fragmentation was optimized, optimization was done for the second fragmentation in
268 the transfer region; collision energies are shown in table 1.

269 Once the samples were acquired, many data were obtained so it was a very tedious task
270 to interpret the spectra. Therefore, MassFragment was used to help in fragment ion
271 assignment. This is a MassLynx tool that works in combination with online chemical
272 databases and consists of comparing the fragmented accurate masses with the fragments
273 expected in a molecule proposed as a candidate. Measured accurate mass of each
274 compound were searched in a chemical database [www.chemspider.com] and different
275 candidates for each mass were found. Then, using the MassFragment tool, a comparison
276 of the accurate masses of the most probable fragments that each candidate generates and
277 the accurate mass of fragments obtained experimentally coming from each mass was

278 done. Finally, the candidate that gave the same accurate mass fragments than the
279 measured experimental mass was assigned. Figure 3 shows an example of one
280 compound identified using this tool. Several candidates were found for accurate mass
281 327.2505(peak number 6, table 3) in the database and 3 accurate mass fragments (figure
282 3) were compared with the accurate mass fragments that the candidates most likely
283 generate. Finally, this mass was assigned to 2-[2-(2-undecoxyethoxy)ethoxy]ethanol.
284 Table 3 shows the new compounds identified using these techniques. It was possible to
285 identify 13 new compounds in the adhesive 3 most of them were esters. As was above
286 explained plasticizers could be esters, so these compounds identified with UHPLC-
287 HDMS could be plasticizers added to acrylic adhesive formulation, which would match
288 with the expected composition.

289

290 **3.3. Qualitative migration studies**

291 Preliminary qualitative migration tests were carried out using Tenax in contact with the
292 laminates prepared from the adhesives under study and using different materials, as was
293 described in the experimental section. Tenax was selected because some of the
294 laminates were made of paper so liquid simulants cannot be used with it.
295 The methanol extract of Tenax was analyzed by UHPLC-MS-TOF with the same
296 UHPLC conditions used in the identification and the results obtained are listed in Table
297 4. As can be seen, 26 compounds were detected. For adhesive 1, 6 NPEO polymers
298 were detected; for adhesive 2, 6 poly (propylene oxide) polymers were detected and for
299 adhesive 3, 14 different compounds were detected. The most important finding here
300 was to demonstrate that even the non volatile compounds could migrate from the
301 laminate to Tenax. Although the migration tests are performed nowadays in any food
302 contact material, almost always the effort is focused on the volatile compounds, as their
303 migration kinetics are likely faster and thus a higher concentration values of migrants
304 are expected in the food. However, in this case the real migration confirms that not only
305 the volatiles but also the non volatile compounds can migrate throughout the laminate to
306 the solid food simulant.

307 The comparison of the NPEO spectra (Figure 2) obtained analyzing the pure adhesives
308 extracts and NPEO spectra obtained in the methanol extract of Tenax after the migration
309 test (Figure 4) shows that only the small polymers corresponding to low masses (331 Da
310 to 551 Da) migrated to the Tenax. This fact confirms the general idea that the migration
311 is mainly governed by the molecular mass and that the smaller molecules can easily
312 cross the materials and be dissolved or adsorbed on the food. Among the NPEO
313 polymers, NPEO2 was found. This compound is considered the most persistent and
314 toxic NPEO metabolite together with NPEO1 and NP [33, 34]. The toxic effect of these
315 compounds is associated to their ability to mimic natural estrogens and disrupt the
316 endocrine systems of living organisms.

317 NPEO is not listed in the annexes of the plastics Directive and its amendments [2]
318 therefore the maximum concentration in a food simulant must be 10 µg/Kg (ppb) [32].
319 In order to have an idea of the NPEO concentration in Tenax, a NPEO standard was
320 analyzed. The result of this semiquantitative experiment provided a concentration value
321 in Tenax close to the limit value of 10 ppb. This work emphasizes even more the
322 importance of removing NPEO from adhesive formulations, as if they are present, they
323 migrate and could appear in the food in contact with the laminate.

324

325 **Conclusion**

326 UHPLC-TOF-MS and UHPLC-HDMS have demonstrated a strong potential for
327 screening and identification of adhesive compounds and proved to be one of the most
328 powerful tools for elucidating unknown compounds present in complex samples. The
329 availability of full scan mass spectra, the possibility of fragmentation of each single
330 mass and accurate mass measurements provided qualitative information that could be
331 used to ascertain many compounds that were present in samples. This is extremely
332 important in food contact materials, as the legislation establishes that even the unknown
333 compounds and those non intentionally added to the packaging materials should be
334 identified. In this case, concentrations around 10 ppb could be expected and those
335 compounds providing higher level of concentration in the food should be deeply
336 investigated and removed from the formulation. In the case of adhesives, where slightly

337 information is known about the formulations, the availability of powerful analytical
338 tools is of paramount importance to ensure the safety in use when being applied to the
339 food packaging materials.

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